

(1H, s, C₆ coumarin proton) and 6.20 (1H, s, C₄ coumarin protons), 7.35 (1H, s, ArH), 6.75 (1H, s, ArH), 2.80, 1.80 (2H each, chroman CH₂CH₂) and 1.40 (6H, s, O-C(CH₃)₂) revealing the presence of a coumarin and chroman ring in the compound. The above spectral data were found to be very similar to those reported for dihydroxanthyletin⁴. The identity of the two compounds was established by comparison of physical constants and uv, ir and nmr spectral data.

Further elution of the column with benzene-chloroform (1:1) mixture yielded a yellow solid crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow leaflets, C₁₆H₁₂O₆ (M⁺ 284), m.p. 210; λ_{max} (EtOH) 260, 272, 290, 415 and 435 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3360 (bonded OH), 1680 (non-chelated C=O), 1625 cm⁻¹ (conjugated chelated C=O); δ 2.30 (3H, s, aromatic C-methyl), 3.90 (3H, s, aromatic methoxyl), 6.90 (2H, s, C₆-H and C₇-H), 7.00 (1H, s, C₈-OH) and 7.40 (1H, s, C₄-H). It responded to methanolic magnesium acetate test for anthraquinones⁴ and was characterised as physcion⁵ by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic sample.

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Phytochemical Examination of the Leaves of *Anacardium occidentale*

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LITERATURE survey showed detailed reports on the bark¹, cashew apple² and nutshell³ of *A. occidentale* for its flavonoidic constituents. However, a scanty work on its leaf constituents prompted

us to investigate the leaves thoroughly. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of myricetin, agathisflavone, robustaflavone, amentoflavone, quercetin, kaempferol, apigenin and two glycosides, viz. quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside and quercetin-3-O-glucoside. The structure of the compounds were confirmed by their spectral data and by comparison with authentic samples.

Dried defatted leaves (2 kg), procured from Mannarghat, Kerla (India), were extracted exhaustively with methanol. The methanol concentrate was refluxed successively with benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone. The chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone concentrates were combined and treated with boiling water. The water-insoluble fraction on tlc examination (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36:9:5) revealed the presence of six bands which were labelled as AO-I to AO-VI, in order of increasing R_f values. They were separated by preparative tlc (B-P-F) and eluted by acetone mixed with pyridine (2%).

AO-I, m.p. 358–59°; AO-IV, m.p. 314°; AO-V, m.p. 278° and AO-VI, m.p. 346° were characterised as myricetin, quercetin, kaempferol and apigenin by comparison of nmr spectral studies of their acetates and methyl ethers with authentic samples⁴. AO-II on methylation was found to be a mixture of two compounds. The two methyl ethers were identified as hexamethyl ethers of agathisflavone⁵ and robustaflavone⁶. AO-III, m.p. 253–55°, on derivatisation gave a hexamethyl ether of amentoflavone, m.p. 226–27° and hexaacetate of amentoflavone, m.p. 240–42°⁷.

The methanol concentrate, after solvent treatment (chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone) was found to be a mixture of two glycosides. They were separated by column chromatography over silica gel column using CCl₄-EtOAc (1:1, 1:4) mixtures as eluting solvent. The resulting two fractions were labelled as AOG-I and AOG-II.

AOG-I, m.p. 181–82°, gave green colour with ferric chloride and positive Molisch and Shinoda tests⁸. The uv spectral studies showed it to be flavonol glycoside with 3-position glycosylated. On acid hydrolysis (6% alcoholic HCl) it gave quercetin and rhamnose. The nmr spectrum of the acetate was comparable to the quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside⁴, which was further confirmed by the hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside using Hakomori method⁹. Similarly AOG-II, m.p. 235–36°, was characterised as quercetin-3-O-glucoside⁴.

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Chemical Examination of the Leaves of

Rhus mysurensis

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THE present paper deals with the study of complex mixture of flavonoids in the leaves extract of *Rhus mysurensis* (Anacardiaceae) procured from the Government Botanical Garden, Ooty (India). While the work was in progress, Sarada and Adinarayana¹ reported the isolation of kaempferol, quercetin, myricetin, hinokiflavone and 3-*O*-rhamnosides of myricetin, quercetin and kaempferol from the leaves of the same species. Our investigations revealed the presence of amentoflavone and cupressuflavone in addition to hinokiflavone, quercetin and kaempferol besides quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside, quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoside and kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside.

The acetone extract of defatted leaves of *R. mysurensis* showed four distinct spots on tlc examination (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5). They were labelled as RM-I to RM-IV and separated by preparative tlc (B-P-F).

RM-I, on methylation was found to be a mixture of three methyl ethers. The two methyl ethers, m.p. 228-29° and 302° were characterised as hexamethyl ethers of amentoflavone² and cupressuflavone³, respectively by their nmr spectral studies; the third methyl ether, m.p. 202°, could not be characterised due to paucity of material.

RM-II, on derivatisation gave a pentacetate, m.p. 240° and a methyl ether, m.p. 260°. It was characterised as hinokiflavone⁴ by comparison of nmr spectra of its acetate and methyl ether with that of an authentic sample. RM-III, m.p. 314°, and RM-IV, m.p. 278° were characterised as quercetin and kaempferol on the basis of uv and nmr spectral studies⁵.

The methanol extract of acetone exhausted leaves on tlc examination (ethyl acetate-ethyl methyl ketone-acetic acid-water, 5 : 3 : 1 : 1) showed three major brown spots under uv light. They were separated by preparative tlc and labelled as RMG-I to RMG-III. All the three compounds gave positive Molisch and Shinoda tests indicating all to be flavonoidic glycosides.

RMG-I, m.p. 231-33°, on acid hydrolysis gave quercetin (m.p. 314°) and glucose. Uv spectral studies of the glucoside showed attachment of the sugar at C-3-hydroxyl of the aglycone. The final confirmation of the sugar attachment was obtained by the identification of partial methyl ether (m.p. 193°) obtained on hydrolysis of methylated glycoside⁶. The RMG-I was therefore identified as quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside. Similarly, RMG-II, m.p. 181-83°, and RMG-III, m.p. 178°, were identified as quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoside and kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside⁷, respectively.

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Occurrence of Aurentiacin in

Didymocarpus podocarpa

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PHYTOCHEMICAL investigation on two *Didymocarpus* species, *D. pedicellata* and *D. aurentiaca* led to the isolation of a number of chalcones¹, quinochalcones², flavanones³, terpenoids⁴ and α -pyrones⁵. Recently, three kaurenoid diterpenes have been reported from another *Didymocarpus* sp., *D. oblonga*⁶. Very recently, one α -pyrone derivative, 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain has also been found to occur in *D. podocarpa*⁷.

Extraction of the whole plant of *D. podocarpa* with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) led to the isolation of a compound, m.p. 141° which was crystallised as orange plates (petroleum ether-benzene) and